

**PARASITES OF *Auchinoglanis occidentalis*, SILURIFORMES, BAGRIDAE) AT RIVERS
NIGER-BENUE CONFLUENCE, LOKOJA, NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

Fish parasites constitute a major problem to fish and fisheries in the tropics. Monthly sampling of catches in Rivers Niger and Benue at the confluence area was carried out between March 2007 and February 2008 to determine the occurrence of parasites in *Auchinoglanis occidentalis* as part of a larger research work on parasites of Siluriformes. A total of 74 fish hosts were examined, 41(55.40%) were infected, while 33(44.59%) were uninfected. Thirteen (13) parasite species were identified. These included 2 protozoans (*Myxobolus* sp. and the Trichodinid ciliates), 1 digenean (metacercaria of *Pygidiopsis genata*), 3 cestodes (*Monobothrioides woodlandii*, *Bothriocephalus acheilognathii*, *Proteocephalus largoproglotis*), 5 nematodes (*Procamallanus laevionchus*, *Rhabdochona congolensis*, *Spinitectus guntheri*, *Oxyuris equi*, *Contracaecum microcephalum*) and 2 acanthocephalan (*Neoechinorhynchus prolixum* and *Acanthella*- the immature stages). The protozoans and the cestode, *Monobothrioides woodlandii* had the highest prevalence among the parasites recovered in this study. *Myxobolus* sp. and the Trichodinid ciliates were recovered from the visceral cavities and gills/skin of fish hosts, respectively. The rest parasites were recovered from the intestines. The relationship of host size (weight/ length) and parasite infection showed there was significant infection ($p < 0.05$) in fish of intermediate size classes. There was however no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in the infection of the sexes, both were equally infected. This study is an attempt to contribute to the knowledge of parasitic fauna of the Bagrid catfish *Auchinoglanis occidentalis* in River Niger and Benue at the Confluence area.

KEYWORDS: *Auchinoglanis occidentalis*, Siluriformes, Nematodes, Protozoans Acanthocephalans, Parasites

Received for Publication: 12/02/14

Accepted for Publication: 20/04/14

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INTRODUCTION

Auchinoglanis occidentalis (Cuvier and Valenciennes) is common in Rivers Niger, Benue and swamps around the confluence area in Lokoja (Iyaji, 2011). Reed (1967) recorded *A. occidentalis* of about 500 mm and up to 4.5kg in size. The fish has good flesh quality and is well accepted and relished by consumers in the confluence area.

A. occidentalis and other fish species are economically important as sources of income to the fishers around the riverine areas. They equally provide high quality proteins (with low cholesterol levels) and easily digestible oils in diets of the populace (Omeji, 2012). The health benefits of fish proteins and oils are increasingly being recognized globally. Intake of fish proteins has been proven to have a protective effect on diabetic renal disease. Mollstein *et al.* (2001) reported that high consumers of fish protein (mean 9.35g/day i.e. 53g fish/day) had lower odds ratio of

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microalbuminuria than individuals consuming less (mean 2.72g/day i.e. 15g fish/day). Similarly, fish oils, comprising mainly of Omega 3 essential fatty acids are necessary for the normal functioning of the brain, heart and in boosting the immune system (Hohn, 1999). These health benefits and the increase in population have led to higher demands on fish production in recent years. However, several factors, among which includes parasitic infections and diseases have limited fish production. Fish harbour parasites which cause a host of pathological debilities in them, resulting in their nutritive devaluation. Parasites also utilize energy otherwise available for their hosts growth, sustenance, development, establishment, reproduction and as such may harm their hosts in a number of ways (Williams, 1967; Echi *et al.*, 2009a,b) and affect their production (Batra, 1984; Marcogliese, 2002).

This study deals with parasite fauna of *Auchinoglanis occidentalis* in Rivers Niger and Benue at the confluence area. Although many research work on the parasites of catfish species have been published as evidenced by the works of Oniye *et al.* (2004), Ezenwaji *et al.* (2005), Akinsaya *et al.* (2008), Iyaji *et al.* (2009), Smith and Luus-Powell (2011), Iyaji (2011), Eyo *et al.* (2012), Omeji (2012), Eyo and Iyaji (2014) among others, more information is still needed on the parasitic fauna of freshwater catfishes, especially at the confluence area of the two major rivers in Nigeria. However, no work has been done on the parasitic fauna of *Auchinoglanis occidentalis* from the Rivers Niger and Benue and its confluence. This study investigated the parasites of the catfish, *Auchinoglanis occidentalis* in the major rivers of Niger and Benue at the confluence area in Lokoja, Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study area is located around the confluence of the two major rivers in Nigeria, Niger and Benue, between latitude 7° 45N to latitude 8° 12N and longitude 6° 39E to longitude 7° 00E (Fig. 1). There are extensive flood plains with numerous perennial ponds and marshes on both banks of the rivers before and within the confluence. The vegetation along the rivers comprises mainly of wooded savanna grassland with shrubs and trees. The climate of the area consists of two seasons, the dry season and wet season. The wet season begins towards the end of March and ends towards the end of October or early November while the dry season begins in November and lasts until late March. Fish were sampled from fishermen using a variety of fishing gears (set nets, cast nets, hooks, gill nets, etc) at the three localities for a period of 12 months and examined for parasites: locality 1: Ohono village, along Lokoja - Koton Karfe road (Niger River); locality 2: Mozum village, located on the eastern bank (Benue River) and locality 3: Ganaja village, below the confluence of the two rivers (confluence).

The procedures for examining fish for parasites were adapted from Arthur and Albert (1994) and Marcogliese (2002). Fish were taken to the laboratory fresh from the sampling sites. In the laboratory, preliminary data recorded were; fish identity (Reed, 1967; Olaosebikan and Raji, 1998), date caught, locality from which the samples were taken and sex of fish hosts (matured specimens). Total length and standard length were measured to the nearest 0.1 cm using a meter rule mounted on a dissecting board, while weight was measured with a digital top loading balance to the nearest 0.1 g. The external surfaces - fins and skins were examined with brush and hand lens for the presence of ectoparasites. The gills were cut and removed, and each gill filament and arch examined with hand lens for the presence of myxosporidean cysts and monogeneans. Fish not examined were kept overnight in refrigerator for examination the following day.

Examination of endoparasites: The abdomen of individual fish was cut open ventrally. The internal organs and visceral cavities were examined for cyst and larval parasites. The guts were removed and placed in Petri dishes. The contents were washed into beakers with normal saline and shaken to remove mucus and other host debris. Parasites were allowed to settle before decanting and the residue examined with compound Olympus microscope. Individual parasites were mounted on slides and viewed under higher magnification (x40) for clearer view and identified. All parasites recovered were recorded.

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Treatment, Preservation and Fixation of Parasites: The parasites obtained were treated, preserved and fixed as follows:

Microscopic parasites: Microscopic parasites were first stained in Haematoxylin and Eosin for 12 hours and transferred to 45% acetic acid for 2 minutes and latter placed in methyl salicylate for 1 minute. The parasites were mounted in Canada balsam on clean slides.

Trematode digeneans: Trematode digenean parasites were placed in water to relax and stretch out fully before being fixed in alcohol formol acetic acid. They were mounted in Canada balsam.

Cestodes: They were fixed in 4% neutral formalin and dehydrated in ethanol. They were then stained with Eosin and mounted whole in Canada balsam.

Nematodes: Nematodes were placed in 70% ethyl alcohol and 5% glycerin added for storage. They were later stained with Eosin and mounted whole in Canada balsam.

Acanthocephalans: Acanthocephalan parasites were left overnight in a refrigerator to relax and exude the proboscis and then fixed in 70% ethanol to dehydrate them. They were then stained in Eosin and mounted on clean slides in Canada balsam.

Identification of parasites: Parasites collected were identified to species level using Yamaguti (1959), Chambrier and Vaucher (1995), Paperna (1996) and Moravec (1998).

Statistical analysis: The ecological terms: prevalence (%), mean intensity and abundance were analyzed according to Bush *et al.* (1997). The relationships between host factors such as sex, weight and standard length and parasite infection were examined from data pooled from the three localities using analysis of variance (ANOVA). All statistical analysis were done using SPSS version 15 for windows.

RESULTS

Examination of 74 *A. occidentalis* hosts revealed that 41(55.40%) were infected while 33(44.59%) were uninfected. There was uneven distribution of fish hosts in the 3 localities. In River Niger (Locality 1), 29 hosts were examined, 19(65.57%) were infected and the total parasites recovered was 105. In River Benue (Locality 2) 26 fish hosts were examined, 14(53.84%) were infected with a total parasite of 167, while in the Confluence (Locality 3), 19 hosts examined, 6(31.50%) were infected and the total parasite recovered was 18 (Fig. 2).

Parasite taxa and species encountered were: the protozoans; *Myxobolus* sp. and the Trichodinid ciliates, the trematode digenean; metacercaria of *Pygidiopsis genata*, the cestodes; *Monobothrioides woodlandii*, *Bothriocephalus acheilognathii* and *Proteocephalus largoproglotis*, the nematodes; *Procamallanus laevionchus*, *Rhabdochona congolensis*, *Spinitectus guntheri*, *Oxyuris equi* and *Contracaecum microcephalum*, the acanthocephalans; *Neoechinorhynchus prolixum* and *Acanthella* (the immature stages).

The helminths were recovered from the intestines while the protozoans; *Myxobolus* sp. and Trichodinids were recovered from the visceral cavities and gills/skin, respectively.

The protozoans had the highest prevalence of 9.45%. The cestode; *M. woodlandii* recorded prevalence of 8.10% and was the highest among the helminths, while the rest prevalence ranged between 1.35% and 6.75% (Table 1).

In the 3 localities, the highest prevalence of 20%, mean intensity of 18.8 ± 5.2 and abundance of 3.8 was recorded by *Myxobolus* sp. in River Benue (Table 2). Infections of *A. occidentalis* by sex showed that males were more

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infected by *Myxobolus* sp while females had more infections by Trichodinids and *R. congolensis*. The rest of the parasites infected both males and females equally with low prevalence. There was no significant difference in the infection of the sexes ($p>0.05$) (Table 3).

In the length categories, most of the parasites occurred in the 11 – 20 cm fish length class, although the highest prevalence of 36% was seen among 21 – 30 cm fish length class (Table 4). There was no significant difference in the infections of parasites in the length categories ($p>0.05$).

Infection of *A. occidentalis* by body weight showed that Trichodinids, *M. woodlandii* and *B. acheilognathii* had the highest prevalence of 20% in 26 – 50g weight class, while *Myxobolus* sp. had the highest prevalence of 19% in 100 +g weight class (Table 5). There was no significant difference in the infections of parasites in the weight categories ($p>0.05$).

DISCUSSION

A. occidentalis from rivers Niger and Benue at the confluence area in Lokoja were parasitized by a number of parasites in the 3 localities studied. *A. occidentalis* from River Niger (Locality 1) had the highest parasite species, involving 5 parasite taxa while River Benue (Locality 2) and Confluence (Locality 3) had 2 and 3 parasitic taxa each with fewer parasite species. The protozoan parasite; Trichodinids and the nematode; *Rhabdochona congolensis* were common across the 3 localities, while other parasites were found in one or two localities. This confirmed the reports of Kennedy *et al.* (1986) that the number of parasites a fish hosts harbour vary widely from one fish to another and from one locality to another. Marcogliese (2002) reported that the distribution of parasites in hosts are almost always aggregated or over dispersed, meaning that most of the parasites in a population maybe found in a small number of hosts and most potential hosts maybe infected or uninfected, though with exceptions. In agreement with the findings of Marcogliese (2002), River Benue, though with fewer hosts infected (14), had the highest number of parasites (167). This also confirmed the reports of Omeji (2012) who recorded overall parasite prevalence of 58.33% in *A. occidentalis* in Lower River Benue at Makurdi, which was higher than the overall parasite prevalence of 55.40% recorded in this study.

The highest prevalence of 9.45% each was recorded for the protozoan parasites (*Myxobolus* sp. and the Trichodinids) found mostly in the visceral cavities and skin/gills, respectively. The infections of these protozoans were in conformity with earlier findings in African freshwater ecosystems. Protozoan parasite infection was variable and generally low in freshwater fish hosts (Paperna, 1973; Sakiti and Bouix, 1987). Paperna (1973) reported low prevalence of 1% from Lake George, Wales, Australia, and Reed *et al.* (2003) reported a prevalence of 14.3% for *Henneguya* sp infecting *Clarias gariepinus* in Okavanga River basin in Botswana, while Kostoungue *et al.* (2001) reported protozoan infection of between 4.4% and 36.8% for fishes from freshwater ecosystem of Chad, Central Africa. Fish hosts infected by protozoan parasites though reported to cause irritation and breathing problems (Klinger and Floyd, 2002) appeared to be in good condition probably because of the low infection rates.

The helminth parasites recorded low prevalence in *A. occidentalis*. The highest prevalence of 8.10% was by a cestode, *M. woodlandii*, while other helminths (nematodes and acanthocephalan) recorded 1.35% and 6.75%, respectively. The nematode parasites though with low prevalence, were variable in *A. occidentalis*. Six species were identified in this study. The diversities of nematode species in freshwater fish hosts had also been reported in other African freshwater ecosystems. Khalil (1971) reported 40 species of adult nematodes, representatives of 9 families from fish in Africa with majority occurring in the alimentary system. Boomker (1982) also reported infections by several nematode species in the stomach of *Clarias gariepinus*, while Eyo *et al.* (2012) recovered four nematode species from *Synodontis batensoda* collected from the same locality as in this study. The low prevalence of helminth parasites in *A. occidentalis* could be due to the feeding habit. Up to 92.25% of the stomach contents of *A. occidentalis* in this study consisted of plant parts, insect parts and digested food materials. Cestode and nematode parasites were found to be more associated with plant debris, digested food materials and mud (Iyaji, 2011).

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Most of the parasites in *A. occidentalis* were found in fish of intermediate length/ weight classes (11-20cm/51-75g), while few parasites were recovered from the large length/ weight classes (21-30cm/76-100+g). The higher prevalence and mean intensity of parasites recorded in fish of intermediate length/weight classes examined indicated the increase in parasitism of *A. occidentalis* with size up to the intermediate size. High prevalence of infection in fish of intermediate weight/length had been reported in several other studies (Hanek and Fernando, 1978 a,b; Fernandez, 1985; Obiekezie *et al.*, 1987; Valtonen *et al.*, 1990, Chapman *et al.*, 2000; Iyaji *et al.*, 2009). In similar studies, Shotter (1973) and Roubal (1990) found higher levels of parasitism in hosts with intermediate lengths and stated that fish acquired the parasites in their youth phase which are eliminated in the fish adult phase, suggesting the possibility of the development of immunological resistance in adults. Chapman *et al.* (2000) found that parasite prevalence increased with host body size only up to 700mm; larger individuals showed lower prevalence. Such a pattern could reflect the premature mortality of infected older individuals (Pennycuik, 1971; Anderson and Gordon, 1982; Gordon and Rau, 1982) or the lower prevalence in larger individuals may be due to the development of immunity with age.

There was no evidence of the influence of sex on parasitic infection of *A. occidentalis*. Both sexes were equally infected. Similar results were reported by Auta *et al.* (1999) for *Synodontis* species in Zaria River, Nigeria, Araoye (2005) for *Synodontis schall* in Asa Lake, Ilorin Nigeria, and Owolabi (2005) for *Synodontis membranaceus* in Jebba Lake, Nigeria. The occurrence of parasites in *A. occidentalis* from Rivers Niger-Benue Confluence, Lokoja, Nigeria is a setback to *A. occidentalis* productivity in the confluence. Parasite invasion and establishment in *A. occidentalis* compromised the efficiency of the fish in preventing further infection, lowered the fish reproductive potentials and feed utilization. Thus, to ensure optimal productivity of fish in the Rivers Niger-Benue Confluence, further studies need to be undertaken in order to ascertain the major route of parasite invasion and proper appropriate measures to ameliorate it.

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Fig 1: Map of the study area showing the confluence of rivers Niger/Benue at Lokoja Nigeria.
Source: Shell Petroleum Development Company map of Nigeria. 2000

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Table 1: Parasitic infestation of *A. occidentalis* at the River-Niger Benue Confluence

Parasite Groups	Parasite Species	Number of Hosts Examined	Number of Hosts Infected	Number of Parasite Recovered	Prevalence (%)	Mean Intensity	Abundance
Protozoans	<i>Myxobolus</i> sp	74	7	137	9.45	19.57±4.47	1.85
	Trichodinids	74	7	85	9.45	12.14±16.26	1.15
Digenean	Metacercaria of <i>P. genata</i>	74	2	7	2.70	3.5±3.54	0.09
Cestodes	<i>M. woodlandii</i>	74	6	27	8.10	4.5±3.33	0.36
	<i>B. acheilognathii</i>	74	1	4	1.35	4	0.05
	<i>P.largoproglotis</i>	74	1	1	1.35	1	0.01
Nematodes	<i>P. laevionchus</i>	74	4	5	5.40	1.25±0.50	0.07
	<i>R congolensis</i>	74	5	15	6.75	3±1.58	0.2
	<i>Spinitectus guntheri</i>	74	1	2	1.35	2	0.03
	<i>Oxyuris equi</i>	74	1	2	1.35	2	0.03
	<i>C. microcephalum</i>	74	3	3	4.05	1	0.04
Acanthocephalans	<i>N.prolixum</i>	74	2	3	2.70	1.5±0.71	0.04
	<i>Acanthella</i>	74	1	1	1.35	1	0.01

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Table 2: Parasitic infestation of *A. occidentalis* at the three localities (River Niger, River Benue and Confluence)

Parasite species	Locality 1, Niger River (N=29)					Locality 2, Benue River (N=26)					Locality 3, Confluence (N=19)				
	A	B	C	D	E	A	B	C	D	E	A	B	C	D	E
<i>Myxobolus sp</i>	2	43	6.9	2.15±2.12	1.5	5	94	19.2	18.8±5.12	3.6	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Trichodinids</i>	2	20	6.9	10±4.24	0.7	4	57	15.4	14.25±22.54	2.2	1	8	5.3	8	0.4
<i>Metacercaria of P. genata</i>	2	7	6.9	3.45±3.54	0.2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>M. woodland</i>	4	21	14	5.25±3.69	0.7	0	0	0	0	0	2	6	11	3±2.83	0.3
<i>B. acheilognathii</i>	1	4	3.4	4	0.1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>P. largoproglotis</i>	1	1	3.4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>P. laevionchus</i>	2	3	6.9	1.5±0.71	0.1	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	11	1	0.1
<i>R. congolensis</i>	1	1	3.4	1	0	3	12	11.5	4±1	0.5	1	2	5.3	2	0.1
<i>Spinitectus guntheri</i>	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	3.84	2	0.1	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Oxyuris equi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	3.84	2	0.1	0	0	0	0	0
<i>C. microcephalum</i>	1	1	3.4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>N. prolixum</i>	2	3	6.9	1	0.1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Acanthella</i>	1	1	3.4	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Key: A = Hosts infected, B = Parasites Recovered, C = Prevalence (%), D = Mean Intensity and E = Abundance

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Table 3: Parasitic infestation of *A. occidentalis* by Standard Length at the River-Niger Benue Confluence

Parasites species	Standard length (cm) groups																			
	0-10 (N=1)					11-20 (N=55)					21-30 (N=14)					30+ (N=4)				
	A	B	C	D	E	A	B	C	D	E	A	B	C	D	E	A	B	C	D	E
<i>Myxobolus sp.</i>	0	0	0	0	0	3	56	5.45	1	1	4	81	28.57	7.4	7.4	0	0	0	0	0
Trichodinids	0	0	0	0	0	3	28	5.45	0.5	1	4	57	28.57	5.2	5.2	0	0	0	0	0
Metacercaria of <i>P. genata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	2	7	3.6	0.1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>M. woodlandii</i>	0	0	0	0	0	6	27	10.9	0.5	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>B. acheilognathii</i>	0	0	0	0	0	1	4	2	0.1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>P. largoproglotis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>P. laevionchus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	4	5	7	0.1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>R congolensis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	5	15	9	0.3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Spinitectus guntheri</i>	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Oxyuris equi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>C. microcephalum</i>	0	0	0	0	0	2	2	4	0	0	1	1	7.14	0.1	0.1	0	0	0	0	0
<i>N. prolixum</i>	0	0	0	0	0	2	3	4	0.1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Acanthella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Key: A = Hosts infected, B = Parasites Recovered, C = Prevalence (%), D = Mean Intensity and E = Abundance

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Table 4: Parasitic infestation of *A. occidentalis* by Sex at the River-Niger Benue Confluence

Parasite species	Male (N=37)					Female (N=37)				
	Number of Hosts Infected	Number of Parasite Recovered	Prevalence (%)	Mean Intensity	Abundance	Number of Hosts Infected	Number of Parasite Recovered	Prevalence (%)	Mean Intensity	Abundance
<i>Myxobolus gariepinus sp</i>	5	91	13.5	18.2±3.70	2.46	2	46	5.40	23±5.66	1.24
<i>Trichodinids</i>	3	23	8.11	7.67±5.51	0.62	4	62	10.8	15.5±21.76	1.67
<i>Metacercaria of P. genata</i>	1	1	2.7	1	0.03	1	6	2.70	6	0.16
<i>M. woodland</i>	3	16	8.11	5.33±4.51	0.43	3	11	8.10	3.67±2.31	0.29
<i>P. laevionchus</i>	2	3	5.41	1.50±0.71	0.08	2	2	5.40	1	0.05
<i>R. congolensis</i>	2	7	5.41	3.50±2.12	0.19	3	8	8.10	2.67±1.53	0.21
<i>N. prolixum</i>	1	2	2.7	2	0.05	1	1	2.70	1	0.02

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Table 5: Parasitic infestation of *A. occidentalis* by body weight at the River-Niger Benue Confluence

Parasite species	Body weight (g) groups																								
	0-25 (N=0)					26-50 (N=12)					51-75 (N=17)					76-100 (N=14)					100+ (N=31)				
	A	B	C	D	E	A	B	C	D	E	A	B	C	D	E	A	B	C	D	E	A	B	C	D	E
<i>Myxobolus. Sp</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	23	5.8	1	1.3	0	0	0	0	0	6	11	19.3	3.7	3.7
<i>Trichodinids</i>	0	0	0	0	0	1	7	8.3	7	0.5	1	8	5.8	0	0.4	0	0	0	0	0	5	70	16.1	2.3	2.3
<i>A. ghanensis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Metacercaria of P. genata</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	7	14.2	1	1	0	0	0	0	0
<i>M. woodlandii</i>	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	8.3	1	0.0	3	16	17.6	1	0.9	0	0	0	0	0	2	10	6.45	0.3	0.3
<i>B. acheilognathii</i>	0	0	0	0	0	1	4	8.3	4	0.3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>P.largoproglotis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	5.8	0	0.1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>P. laevionchus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	5.8	0	0.1	1	2	7	0	0	2	2	7	0.1	0.1
<i>R congolensis</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	5.8	0	0.1	0	0	0	0	0	4	13	12.9	0.4	0.4
<i>Spinitectus guntheri</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	5.8	0	0.1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Oxyuris equi</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	5.8	0	0.1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>C.. microcephalum</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	3	9.60	0.1	0.1
<i>Acanthocephalus</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>N. prolixum</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	5.8	0	0.1	1	1	7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
<i>Acanthella</i>	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	5.8	0	0.1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Key: A = Hosts infected, B = Parasites Recovered, C = Prevalence (%), D = Mean Intensity and E = Abundance

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Fig. 2: Distribution of parasites in A. from the three localities

